

Article

The Problems of Dokra Artisans in the Age of Globalization: A Case Study at Bikna and Dariapur in W.B.

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Abstract

India has a history of rich and diverse cultural tradition. And among its diversity, the legacy of India's craft culture always occupies a special place owing to its beauty, dignity, form, style and aesthetics. With the onset of globalization there are enough opportunities for Indian hand made products made by its skillful artists in both the home and foreign markets. Although Indian folk crafts have been benefited enormously, many of its forms have been facing extinction in the globalized/liberalized market economy. The product of dokra artisans are also in great demand in domestic and foreign markets because of their primitive simplicity, enchanting folk motifs and forceful form. This is despite the fact that the demand for their products is very high including in international markets, the dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur are facing a lot of problems. To highlight the basic problems of dokra crafts and artisans facing in the age of globalization is the theme of this article.

Keywords: Globalization, Folk Craft, Dokra, Lost-wax-casting.

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Introduction

Globalization is the so-called buzz word used extensively to refer to the socio-cultural and economic processes that have been dominating the current juncture in world history. Globalization was introduced to India in 1990s, when the Indian government introduced a set of reforms like Liberalization, Privatization etc. The multinational corporations were brought in by globalization. Since 1991, we have seen major changes in India. Because globalization has opened India to the world in the much needed exposure. Globalization has had a very profound impact on Indian culture and this can be seen every aspect of life. Since its advent in 1991, India has experienced both positive and negative impacts of globalization process. With the onset of globalization there are enough opportunities for Indian hand made products made by its skillful artists in both the home and foreign markets. Although Indian folk crafts have been benefited enormously, many of its forms have been facing extinction in the globalized/liberalized market economy. The state of condition of the rural artisans is critical and they have been mere spectators of the developmental process. It is the age in which many folk arts either undergo change in their form, or totally disappear. The 'Dokra' folk craft and dokra artisans of Bikna (Bankura District) and Dariapur (Burdwan District) in West Bengal are also facing enormous problems in this era of globalization. The purpose of this paper is to address the basic problems of dokra crafts and artisans facing in the age of globalization.

Methodology

This study is primarily empirical. But both primary and secondary data have been effectively used in this study. Secondary data were collected from various documents such as books, magazines, journals, old research papers as well as from internet. Primary data were collected from two dokra villages in two districts of West Bengal. These are Bikna in Bankura district and Dariapur in Burdwan district. The techniques of primary data collection were observation method and unstructured Interview Schedule.

Globalization and Folk crafts:

Globalization has become one of the most debated topics and key area of research among the policy makers, statesmen, corporate, politicians and academia respectively over the past few years. According to Malcom Waters¹, the word 'global' is over 400 years old and the common usage of such words as 'globalization', 'globalize' and 'globalizing' did not begin until about 1960. He said that, in 1961 'Webster' became the first major dictionary to offer definitions of 'globalism' and 'globalization'. Globalization has been defined in different way. Waters² offers his definition of globalization as "A social process in which the constraints of geography on social and cultural arrangements recede and in which people become increasingly aware that they are receding." Anthony Giddens³ explains that, "Globalization refers to the fact that we all increasingly live in one world, so that individuals, groups and nations become interdependent." According to Harold James⁴ "globalization is the increased involvement of interchanges, accelerated by the advanced improvement of technology and communications, between people, goods, capital and ideas and culture." Y.Singh⁵ discussed the concept of globalization as a composite process. It results from the convergence of a series of development in society which is qualitatively new. These include: contemporary revolution in science and technology of communication, high velocity movements of finance, capital and market, increased social mobility, migration of personnel and the emergence of a global diaspora. He said that, its associated contributory processes are: intensification of cultural interaction among diverse groups through media exposure, increased incidence of leisure-time activities, growth in tourism, infrastructures of entertainment and marketing of cultural products, personnel and styles.

Globalization is composed of three main dimensions: Economic globalization, Political globalization, Cultural globalization.

Economic globalization refers to the intensification

and stretching of economic interrelations around the globe. It encompasses such things as the emergence of a new global economic order, the internationalization of trade and finance, the changing power of transnational corporations, and the enhanced role of international economic institutions⁶.

Political globalization refers to the intensification and expansion of political interrelations around the globe. Aspects of political globalization include the modern-nation state system and its changing place in today's world, the role of global governance, and the direction of our global political systems⁷.

Cultural globalization refers to the intensification and expansion of cultural flows across the globe. Cultural globalization refers to the transmission of ideas, meanings and values across world space. This process is marked by the common consumption of cultures that have been diffused by the Internet, popular culture, and international travel. The circulation of cultures enables individuals to partake in extended social relations outside the borders. The creation and expansion of such social relations is not merely observed on a material level. Cultural globalization involves the formation of shared norms and knowledge with which people associate their individual and collective cultural identities, and increasing interconnectedness among different populations and cultures.

From any of the point of view as far as explaining globalization is concerned—be it Economic, Political or Cultural, it can be viewed in the light of homogenization, or heterogenization/hybridization. For example, when we view culture in the light of homogenization, it refers to the convergence toward a common set of cultural traits and practices⁸. Cultural homogenization is the homogenization of different cultural practices into one blended, uniform cultural practices that do not allow easy identification of the characteristics of many cultures. It means over the years, peoples of two or more cultures have interacted and intermingles in such a manner as to lose their

individual cultural identities and merged into a one uniform culture than does not show any trace of diversity of different cultures among the people. On the other hand, hybridization thesis focuses on the intercultural exchange and the incorporation of cultural elements from a variety of sources within particular cultural practices⁹ .

India opened up its economy and adapted to globalization in the early 1990s. Major changes initiated as a part of the liberalization and globalization strategy included scrapping of the industrial licensing regime, reduction in the number of areas reserved for the public sector, amendment of the monopolies and restrictive trade practices act, start of the privatization programme, reduction in tariff rates etc. Since the advent of globalization in 1991, India has undergone many changes in different spheres. In the days of McDonalds, Pepsi, Cola and Levi's jeans, where free flow of goods and services and also of people and culture have been rampant, the volatility of the choice of the variety-seeking consumers, the king in the age of globalization not only always demands the new and modern but also sometimes revamps the old and the traditional. It is here the case for traditional arts and crafts comes to the fore¹⁰ . India has a history of rich and diverse cultural tradition. And among its diversity, the legacy of India's craft culture always occupies a special place owing to its beauty, dignity, form, style and aesthetics. Actually folk craft sometimes more precisely expressed as artisanal handicraft, is any of a wide variety of types of work where useful and decorative objects are made completely by hand or by using only simple tools. It is a traditional main sector of craft, and applies to a wide range of creative and design activities that are related to making things with one's hands and skill, including work with textiles, moldable and rigid materials, paper, plant fibers, etc. Usually the term is applied to traditional techniques of creating items (whether for personal use or as products) that are both practical and aesthetic¹¹. With the onset of globalization there are enough opportunities for Indian hand made products made by its skillful artists in both the home and foreign markets. During the globalization phase, the growth in handicrafts

sector amounts to increasing demand for ethnic and culture-specific goods as a result of growth in world tourism. Although Indian folk crafts have been benefited enormously, many of its forms have been facing extinction in the globalized/liberalized market economy. The state of condition of the rural artisans is critical and they have been mere spectators of the developmental process. According to Jha & Singh¹² " Globalization of markets has led to conversion of traditional objects of art and aesthetics having mostly ritual uses in the local communities into marketable commodities . This has not only rapidly disrupted the autonomy of folk cultures , but also destabilised the life of the artisans by creating new networks of competitions and price was and a new class of exploitative middleman It has disrupted the balance in the cultural , social and economic life of many communities including tribes , artisans , and traditional cultural performers etc . Being in minority and economically vulnerable , these communities suffer loss of their cultural identity the most in the process of globalization ". In the era of globalization, the dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur also facing a lot of problems. Before discussing their problems I am giving a short description about 'Dokra' craft and the technique of making these folk craft.

Dokra craft

Dokra (also spelt Dhokra) is non-ferrous metal casting using the lost-wax casting technique. Dokra metal casting is one of the oldest traditional techniques of metal casting in India. This sort of metal casting has been used in India for over 4,000 years and is still used. Dokra is the art of metal crafts among some aboriginal tribes of eastern India. The tribes were initially nomadic in nature. This nomadic group of people finally settled in the different tribal parts of Indian provinces like Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, and West Bengal. In Bengal the groups are found in the tribal regions of Purulia, Bankura, Birbhum, Bardhaman/Burdwan and Medinipur. The product of dokra artisans are in great demand in domestic and foreign markets

because of primitive simplicity, enchanting folk motifs and forceful form. Its motifs are mostly drawn from folk culture. Untrained in formal institutions, the skill and aesthetic sense of these people are the result of the innate and instinctive creative sense evolved over thousands of years. Their chief identity (Dokra) lay in making these folk crafts. Dokra horses, elephants, peacocks, owls, religious images (like Goddess Durga, Laxmi, Saraswati and Lord Sri Krishna, Shiva, Kartik, Ganesh etc.), measuring bowls, tribal jewelry, tribal doll, and lamp , chains, caskets, etc., are highly appreciated .

Dokra craft

Fig.4. Measuring bowls] Fig.5. Image of Goddess Durga

Fig.1 Owl

Photos by Author

Fig.3 Tribal doll Fig.2. Tribal ornament

Raw materials

Brass metal, Bell metal, Bees wax (mohum), Clay bees-wax threads, Coal, mustard oil, 'dhuna' (extracted from the Sal tree).

Tools

Furnace (bhatti), Sulka (to give impressions), Small chisel (nihan), Big chisel (batani), Hammer, Graphite container to melt brass (kui), Tongs (chimta).

The Technique

Dokra artists use a very interesting method to cast metal into the craft, a technique that is known as 'Cire Perdue' or 'lost wax' process. This technique is almost as old as settled civilization. There are two main processes of lost wax casting: solid casting, and hollow casting. While the former is predominant in the south of India the latter is more common in Central and Eastern India. Solid casting does not use a clay core but instead a solid piece of wax to create the mould; hollow casting is the more traditional method and uses the clay core. Artisans of Bikna and Dariapur use hollow casting method. The first task in the lost wax hollow casting process consists of developing a clay core which is roughly the shape of the final cast image. The core is then left to dry either in sunlight or burnt to be backed. Then a wax layer is coated on this core to the thickness of the intended article. The wax model is then coated with another thin layer of clay and every detail of the intricacies is minutely imprinted on this clay layer. After the clay gets dry more layers of clay are added to the remaining mould to make it much thicker and harder. Then the entire mould is preheated to melt the wax and consequently extracted it to leave the mould with a cavity with single or multiple channels. A molten metal is poured into the cavity through the channels there after which subsequently takes the shape of the aimed article. Then the entire mould is left to cool in shade and finally the clay cores are broken to reveal the original artifact. The traces of the clay

are then removed and defects are repaired. These simple steps are being followed since the very primitive age with unflinching success for generating the rare and precious art pieces¹³

Problems Facing the Dokra craft and Dokra artisans

A unique feature of 'Dokra' art is that no two pieces are identical, reason lies in the fact that each piece is hand-made and hence, is distinct. This art form is widely appreciated and is wooing art lovers across the globe. The products have a world wide appeal owing to their primitive simplicity, enchanting folk motifs and forceful form. Dokra art is used for figurines and statues while dokra art jewelry is also very famous and becoming popular among younger generation. The main hallmark of Dokra craft is enchanting folk motif, primitive simplicity, a rustic beauty and imaginative designs and patterns. The distinctive appearance of Dokra craft is due to its antique and stark finish and rustic look - both of which are widely coveted in domestic markets and in global international art markets. There is emerging a new market in United States and UK. The fashion stores of Milan, Paris, London are looking for these unique Dhokra articles. With changing times, e-marketing has become very effective. A number of e-commerce sites have Dokra products on sale. The Dokra artisans have good skill and also put in a lot of hard work. But they miss out on having exposure to the change in trends, marketing hence over the years have not been able to achieve a stable position. According to Sourish Bhattacharya 14, "The Dokra craftsmen of Bengal are probably facing the most wretched condition among all of the Dokra artisans of the country. Though they cultivate a valuable treasure of art, they are least recognized as honorable persons among all the other communities of craftsmen. These socially outcast people are also the poorest among the whole metal smith communities. They are most technologically backward section among all of them. They are so poor they cannot even manage a one square meal of food everyday for themselves. Even for their abject caste status they

suffer a lot of humiliation and rebuke which force them to leave this job and many of them have diverted to other occupation to get relieved from this eternal shame." Pravas Sen¹⁵ argued that, "Perhaps the poorest craft group of West Bengal, the Dhokras are the most interesting and creative. In recent years, under the pressure of all embracing industrialization and changing social values they have been forced by the loss of their natural rural market to diversify their products and are now seeking, with the help of the government and some voluntary agencies, a market among urban sophisticates, as creators of decorative ware. These efforts have met with only limited success." This is despite the fact that the demand for their products is very high including in international markets, the dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur are facing a lot of problems. These are:

1. The Dokra Kamaras suffer from poverty, mal - nutrition, and sanitation. High instance of liquor addiction is prevalent. Illiteracy is also a major reason of their state.
2. The increasing price of raw material is forcing the dokra artisans to be less interested in creating these articles with same vigour.
3. Rising price of the end product is attracting less buyers which is a disappointing matter for these artisans.
4. Lack of knowledge about the new designs that are being experimented all over the world, lack of inspiration to work with something new, lack of encouragement to work with innovative ideas are great hindrance to adapting modernizations and keeping pace with contemporary demand.
5. Dokra crafts, which are produced with traditional skill, are under threat of steep decline because of competition from the cheaper machine made local substitutes and imports, which give greater uniformity and better finish.
6. All weather shed for workshop is absent. So, during monsoon it becomes difficult for them to work.
7. The majority of artisans are not aware about various new schemes like loan at minimum rates, free tools and chemical, work shed-cum-housing facilities etc provided by government and NGOs. Illiteracy often makes them more vulnerable.
8. Like most traditional crafts people, the dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur have no formal system of apprenticeship. Craft training as such does not exist.
9. Following the same primitive techniques and having no access to modern technology and infrastructure, is causing a delay in production which is unmatched with this fast moving age.
10. Dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur use traditional furnace. According to Kochhar & Smith¹⁶ --"The traditional furnace was inefficient in two ways: Firstly it was wasteful on fuel. Each furnace was specially built for a single batch production. Fuel was wasted heating the furnace and the moulds of casting temperature, and these was no gain from multiple firing in the same oven, thereby conserving heat. Again, this would not have been a problem to forest living nomads with ready access to free wood, but was immediately disadvantageous once the dhokra had settled down. Secondly, it was more or less impossible to control the firing temperature of the furnace. This meant that metal, particularly zinc, was lost by sublimation when the moulds were broken open. This could be seen in the colour of the fume after opening. The loss of metal led to serious metallurgical degradation of the brass, as well as being another source of cost inefficiency. Another side effect is that ,many of the people of Bikna suffer from eye problems, probably due to heavy metal irritation."
11. According to Kochhar & Smith ¹⁷, the fact that the cire perdue process (lost wax casting) followed in Bikna does not permit wax recovery is a significant factor undermining the potential profitability of the craft. The finest medium for cire perdue modelling is, as the name itself would suggest, beeswax (Mom). The Bikna artisans' preferred medium is Dhuna (a mixture of the resin of the sal tree and mustard oil). This is almost as good as wax but rather cheaper. Whereas artisans

in other parts of India (notably in Bastar and Tamil Nadu) developed efficient means of wax recovery, the Bankura artisans did not. This added to the uncontrolled costs due to the metallurgical problems associated with the traditional furnace.

12. The artisans face a number of difficulties to get loan from banks which results in unwillingness to get loan from banks and they are attracted to local money lenders who finance them with high interest rate.

13. Globalization has induced expansion of world market of dokra crafts. But the problem is the original artisans are not able to make a profit. Rather, it is the intermediaries who make the maximum profit by purchasing the craft at a very low price and by selling at a high price on the contrary. The illiterate artists failing to deal with the modern market system take the help of these middle men who pocket the actual surplus. As a result the artisans gradually become poorer though their products become highly demanding in both home and international markets. It has compelled some of the poor artists to sift to and adopt a more viable occupation.

14. Ineffective and unprofessional infrastructure of the cooperatives found at Bikna and Dariapur region gather low profit margin for the artisans. A little more organized approach from cooperatives might have fetched a little more profit to the artisans.

15. Most of the dokra artisans are extremely poor, and their economic condition has caused many families to leave the craft to find wage employment in local manufacturing centres or in metropolitan centres such as Kolkata.

16. There has been some decline in the domestic demand for the dokra products with the change in people's tastes caused by globalization.

17. In the era of globalization and changing the tastes and fashion, different crafts products have been undergoing change and adopted innovation. In market economy, emphasis is given to the consumption pattern of the people. If the customer wants a product, it must be available,

even if the social costs are high. So the artists are bringing in changes in different craft product products to meet the demands of the people. But the problem arises when originality is lost in the process of innovation. It has been that competition amongst the artisans, use the low quality inputs. As a result, demand of the craft become low.

18. A burning problem in front of the dokra artisans is to protect their own cultural identity. During past few years a group of outsider businessmen(who actually not belong to dokra community) have set up factories where similar kind of products are produced and get traded in various market within and outside India. This actually creates competition for the real artisans who with minimum support of traditional tools and method become unable to compete with those better finished products manufactured at those factories.

Concluding remarks

The study shows that during the present day of globalization, the dokra artisans of Bikna and Dariapur have enough opportunities in the home and global markets. But the precarious condition of the artists needs careful intervention. In the present globalized and financial liberalized market, Indian handicraft industry in general and dokra craft in particular is facing enormous problems. But a few steps still have to be taken as measures to revive this exquisite practice:

Dokra artisans face several problems in marketing. In view of shortage of financial resources, advertising publicity cannot be undertaken by artisans. Absence of systematic marketing network has been a discouraging factor in this sector. Hence it is suggested that the government required to play a vital role in solving the marketing problems faced by the artisans.

The age-old reliance of the poor artisans on middlemen and money lenders for getting the raw materials and selling the finished products should be diminished, if not eliminated.

Voluntary associations also need to put sincere effort for the better working condition of the dokra artisans.

Care should be taken to ensure that with innovation originality of the craft is truly maintained.

Design registration should be done. Then no one can copy it.

If Government exempts dokra products from sales tax, it will result in reduction of crafts prices and thereby increase the sales.

The artisans could be taught to innovate and improvise, use better tools and better raw materials. Innovative techniques can be taught to the workers through government sponsored programmes.

It is often complained that price of dokra products are not uniform. In this situation the customer feels exploited and harassed. This might have bad reputation on the demand of the products. So, categorization of art in each craft should be done according to the skill exhibited and quality of raw materials used and pricing should be made accordingly by a team of experts.

Care should also be taken to popularize crafts in home markets creating awareness among the home consumers.

A sustained and long drawn-out initiative/counseling on alcohol de-addiction should be done.

Hopefully happy times lie ahead for Dokra crafts and artisans can look forward to a bright future.

Notes:

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² Ibid.p3.

³ Giddens ,Anthony(2006): *Sociology*,5th edition; Polity Press;Cambridge CB21UR, UK.p50.

⁴ James,Harold(2004):Globalization; Encyclopedia of American Studies; Grolier Online. Retrieved Feb10,2014, from <http://gnae.ntue.edu.tw/artportal/images/Osub/19/19-6pdf>.

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⁶ From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Globalization>. Retrieved 11 feb 2014.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Wittgenstein, Ludwig (2006, May23): *Culture and Globalization: Polarization, Homogenization, Hybridization*(part 2); <http://www.adifferentportrait.blogspot.com/2006-10-01-archive.html>.

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¹⁰ Jena Pradeep Kumar (Nov.2007): Orissa Handicrafts in the Age of Globalisation : Challenges and Opportunities; Orissa Review * November – 2007; Retrieved Feb 10,2014,from <http://www.orissa.gov.in/e-magazine/Orissareview/nov-2007/engpdf/Pages12-16.pdf>.

¹¹ From *Wikipedia*, the free encyclopedia .Retrieved on 4 feb,2014, from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Folk_craft,

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¹³ *Bhattacharya,Sourish(2011): Dhokra Art and Artists of Bikna: Problems and Prospects. Chitrolekha International Magazine on Art and Design, ISSN 2231-4822, Vol 1, No 2,Kolkata,India.* <http://ibnlive.in.com/news/dokra-craftsmen-left-in-lurch/215066-60-117.html>

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Sen,P(1994): *Craft of West bengal* , Mapin Publishing, Ahmedabad.

¹⁶ Kochhar,Rajesh(2004,sept6): *Dhokra(lost-wax)metal casting craft in eastern India*. Paper presented at WAITRO Conference,Nairobi. <http://rajeshkochhar.com/2008/12/dhokra-lost-wax-metal-casting-craft-in-eastern-india/>

¹⁷ Ibid.